

Analysis of Embedding Gate in the Drain Side in the Electrical Characteristics of SOI MESFET's by an Additional Oxide Region

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Abstract: In this paper, a proposed structure is presented, simulating the effect of gate recess on the drain side in a metal-semiconductor field-effect transistor (MESFET) using silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology with an additional oxide layer. By implementing a recess in the gate, an 18% increase in breakdown voltage, a 2.5-fold increase in drain current, and a 128% increase in maximum output power compared to the structure of the metal-semiconductor field-effect transistor in silicon-on-insulator technology with additional oxide without gate recess (the comparable structure) have been achieved. The results of this paper demonstrate an improvement in device performance for high-voltage and high-power applications.

Keywords: Metal-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor (MESFET), Silicon-On-Insulator (SOI) Technology, Breakdown Voltage

1. Introduction

Power devices play a crucial role in enhancing power amplification, switching speed, and voltage tolerance in electronic circuits [1,2]. Consequently, these devices are widely utilized in military, telecommunications, microwave, and electronics industries. To improve the fundamental parameters of power devices, two approaches are proposed:

The first method involves using new materials in the construction of these devices to replace traditional materials such as germanium and silicon, thereby addressing their limitations. The second approach focuses on implementing structural changes in power devices that lead to improvements in key parameters, including drain current, breakdown voltage, output power, and the device's ability to operate at high frequencies and power levels [1,2].

In MESFET transistors, the Schottky junction replaces the gate oxide, allowing these transistors to be employed in high-power and high-voltage applications [1,2]. However, devices fabricated using silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology face two significant drawbacks: low breakdown voltage and self-heating phenomena.

Several methods have been proposed to enhance the performance of MESFET devices [1,2]. In the proposed structure of this paper, the primary objective is to improve the electrical characteristics of the device, specifically increasing the breakdown voltage, drain current, and ultimately the output power. To achieve this, a structure named SOIMESFET is introduced, featuring a recessed gate on the drain side, along with an additional insulating layer in the channel beneath the drain, extending close to the gate adjacent to the buried oxide layer.

In the second section of this paper, we will introduce the simulated device, providing relevant parameters for its construction and

principles of operation. The following section will compare the electrical characteristics of the proposed device with those of previous devices. Finally, in the fourth section, we will present the results of the work conducted to enhance the electrical characteristics of the proposed device.

2. Structure of the Device and Its Operating Principles

In this section, we will examine the structure of the simulated device and the comparable device, along with their operating principles.

2.1. Device Structure

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the schematic of the simulated device (DS-OR-SOIMESFET) and the comparable device (OR-SOIMESFET), respectively. Both structures are made of silicon carbide (SiC) and feature an additional oxide layer composed of silicon oxide (SiO₂), adhered to the buried oxide layer. Moreover, the new structure includes a recess on the drain side.

To ensure a more accurate comparison, the dimensions of both structures are identical, as detailed below: Gate Length (L_G): 0.6 μm Drain Length (L_D): 0.3 μm Source Length (L_S): 0.3 μm Gate-Source Distance (L_{GS}): 0.5 μm Gate-Drain Distance (L_{GD}): 0.5 μm Length of Oxide on Buried Oxide (L): 0.6 μm Height of Oxide (H): 0.6 μm Distance from the Edge of the Added Oxide on the Right Side (D): 1.6 μm Channel Thickness (T_c): 0.25 μm Oxide Thickness (T_o): 0.5 μm Substrate Thickness (T_s): 0.75 μm Source-Drain Doping Concentration (N_D): $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ Channel Doping Concentration (N_D): $1.5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ Body Doping Concentration (N_A): $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ To create a drift region, a recess of 0.05 μm is introduced in the channel. The Schottky junction of the gate is made of nickel with a work function of 1.5 eV, while the source and drain contacts are made of aluminum. The

breakdown voltage in this area. According to Figure 3, the breakdown voltage of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure is greater than that of the OR-SOIMESFET structure. This can be attributed to the gate recess and the reduction of channel thickness beneath the gate on the drain side (as shown in Figures 4 and 5), which leads to a decrease in the maximum electric field in this structure and the breakdown phenomenon at the gate corner near the drain [8].

Figure 4: Maximum electric field in the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure.

Figure 5: Maximum electric field in the OR-SOIMESFET structure.

The cross-sectional view of the electric field intensity in the DS-OR-SOIMESFET and OR-SOIMESFET structures is shown in Figures 6 and 7. As seen in Figure 6, the electric field intensity beneath the gate on the drain side is significantly high in the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure.

Figure 6: Electric field intensity in the cross-section of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure.

Figure 7: Electric field intensity in the cross-section of the OR-SOIMESFET structure.

According to Figure 3, the breakdown voltage of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure is 130V, while the breakdown voltage of the OR-SOIMESFET structure is

110V. This increase in breakdown voltage makes the device suitable for use in higher power applications.

In Figure 8, the drain current is shown relative to the drain-source voltage at $V_{GS} = 0.5V$ for both the DS-OR-SOIMESFET and OR-SOIMESFET structures.

As seen in this figure, the saturated drain current in the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure is approximately $21 \mu A$, which represents a significant increase compared to the OR-SOIMESFET structure, which has a current of $8.5 \mu A$. This increase of 2.5 times can be attributed to the presence of additional oxide on the drain side.

Figure 8: Output characteristic of drain current versus drain voltage for the DS-OR-SOIMESFET and OR-SOIMESFET structures.

One of the most important applications of FET devices is signal amplification in power amplifiers. As a power amplifier, the device operates in the saturation region of the I-V curve (Class A). The maximum output power for a Class A amplifier is derived from the following equation:

$$P_{max} = \frac{I_{Dsat}(V_B - V_{knee})}{8}$$

In this equation, I_{Dsat} is the saturated drain current, V_{knee} is the knee voltage, and V_B is the breakdown voltage. The above relation is

used to calculate the maximum output power of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET and OR-SOIMESFET structures and to compare them. It is observed that, due to the increase in drain current and breakdown voltage, the maximum output power of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure has increased by 128% compared to the OR-SOIMESFET structure.

4. Conclusion

In this article, a structure of the SOIMESFET transistor with an additional oxide piece attached to the buried oxide layer and a recessed gate on the drain side (DS-OR-SOIMESFET) was proposed and compared with the OR-SOIMESFET structure. The results show that the breakdown voltage in the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure has increased by 18% compared to the OR-SOIMESFET structure due to the reduction of channel width on the drain side. The saturated drain current for the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure has increased by approximately 2.5 times compared to the OR-SOIMESFET structure. Additionally, in the proposed structure, the maximum output power has increased by 128%. Therefore, the simulation results indicate improved electrical characteristics of the DS-OR-SOIMESFET structure compared to the OR-SOIMESFET structure.

The results of these studies can be utilized in the optimal design of semiconductor metal transistors based on silicon-on-insulator technology in telecommunications, high voltage, and high-frequency applications.

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